

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

WELARD JAY C. VICERA, MST

Instructor III

Sultan Kudarat State University

welardjayvicera@sksu.edu.ph

“THE ALGEBRA OF MORNINGS”

The sun emerges with still restraint,
A variable in time and place.
Each yawn, a constant that I must not alter,
Still solving sleep within my zone.

Measuring the toast-to-burn,
I compute, find the dials, and learn.
A liquid proof in porcelain state,
coffee pours in measured rates.

In the mirror, a weary face reflects and unknowns,
I try each day to track.
What is the slope of mood this day?
Can energy be graphed in this way?

With backpacks filled and doors agape,
patterned stride paces with stepped fall.
School zones like problem-sets laid out,
there's rhythm in rules, no regret.

Stepping the same old street,
life silently sums, thoughts conjured in secret—and
The algebra of mornings discloses,
even the gentle edges of chaos know.